

DAILY WALKS TRAIN FUTURE LEADERS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Gemba is a Japanese word meaning the actual place where value-creating work happens. Many leaders use gemba for solving problems, visiting only when there is an issue. Others practice gemba walks on a daily basis to follow up and monitor the situation. However, gemba is really a principle for managing, developing and improving people and processes. It is a valuable tool that helps lean practitioners learn the true facts so they can base management decisions on the actual situation.

In his book *Managing to Learn*, John Shook described the gemba as any setting in which individuals are creating value for the customer. This description goes beyond the manufacturing shop floor, which is how most lean practitioners describe the term.

By going to the place where work is done, leaders gain firsthand, personal knowledge so they can understand the real situation and what needs to be fixed. After all, processes cannot be analyzed or understood from offices. Managing performance data from a distance carries huge negatives for leaders, as such practices could hide the reality of the situation. Leaders who have been at the gemba can make decisions and take responsibility for problem-solving – and that is the surest way to train future leaders.

Many organizations are developing a standard for their leaders that includes checklists for what should be observed during the gemba walk. More important for every department is to create value for the customer at the gemba by eliminating the non-value-added work that increases the product price, reduces quality and delays delivery.

Don't rush the solution

Take the example of a fertilizer company that struggles with machine downtime. The issue, which involved a poorly performing centrifugal fan, reduced production availability by 20 percent. The fan vibrated a lot and suffered balancing issues. By shutting down the fan for balancing four times in a month, the company lost thousands of dollars from production and maintenance.

Everyone in the factory believed that this was a direct maintenance problem related to machine balancing, so maintenance should design a solution. Instead of moving forward on that belief, a kaizen team was assigned to observe the situation. After two days at the gemba analyzing the process, the team concluded that the problem was a process design issue. And of the two process issues causing the difficulties,

neither involved the fan. The fertilizer company needed to fix the process to eliminate the downtime instead of concentrating on the fan, which would have kept the issue at the problem-fix cycle. Without real observation at the gemba, the kaizen team could not have realized the true issue.

This example reveals how many problems are hidden and cannot be discovered from reading the performance data. If a machine is waiting for loading, the problem could include having no orders to process, transportation issues, a work-in-process inventory issue or all of the above. Downtime could have associated activities such as searching for tools, searching for spare parts, waiting for operators and other issues. In any case, production wastes need to be eliminated to reduce lead-times and meet the customer takt time (the customer demand rate). Employees who do the work each day should be taught how to surface these issues in a visual board so leaders can see them and support improvements.

The basic steps of any problem-solving process through the plan-do-check-act (PDCA) cycle are:

1. Define the problem relative to the ideal (plan).
2. Break down the problem into manageable pieces (plan).
3. Find the root cause of the problem (plan).
4. Set the targets for achievement (plan).
5. Select the suitable solution from different countermeasures (plan).
6. Implement the plan (do).
7. Revise the outcomes as expected (check).
8. Find out what is going wrong, adapt, adjust and then repeat the cycle (act).

As you can see, the plan phase is invoked five times before proceeding to the do phase. This is to ensure both the quality of the implementation and that the selected countermeasure will solve the problem. The plan phase cannot be

created without a daily observation at the gemba. And finding the root cause of any issue requires a deep observation at the gemba, gathering facts, discussing things with the process operators and developing the best countermeasure from different alternatives.

Unfortunately, many leaders would jump into the do phase without spending enough time observing the situation to find the root cause. The most enjoyable part for the leader is the “do,” but jumping to the do means not enough time has been spent on understanding. A quick fix might not solve the real problem and could create wastes in other linked areas.

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Proper lean decision-making assesses a set of potential countermeasures rather than just one approach. This minimizes risk and allows people who do the work to discuss different ideas from a wide range of potential scenarios to implement the best solution, a fix that will solve the issue without creating other problems or wastes. Often, those countermeasures are first developed and taken from different people at the gemba.

After selecting and testing the countermeasures, the continuous improvement leader should draw a Gantt chart and define target deadlines based on the recommendation of people who do the work. Define the rest of the activities, such as who will do the plan, how they will develop the plan, and when and how the work will be done. Finally, assign responsibilities for each deliverable and confirm targets and dates.

In recent decades, the quality issue often has been tackled via Six Sigma improvement initiatives. Six Sigma collects data and runs it through statistical component-correlation, regression and analysis for variation. Even though some output results are statistically significant, in many cases Six Sigma teams don't truly understand what is going on.

At Toyota, rather than immediately turning to complex statistical tools, the genchi genbustu process (shortened

to gemba, also meaning “go and see where the work is done”) and other simple analysis tools are tackling the issue of quality. With quality problems, the intention from the gemba visit should be revising the work against the standard, monitoring the operator’s work, understanding the reasons by asking the “five whys,” benchmarking the process with others, reviewing the standard process chart and updating it accordingly to prevent the error in the future.

Improving the output of the gemba visit

Without clear standards, it is difficult for a manager to get much out of a gemba visit. The more established the standards, the more productive the visit. Companies that want to develop their leaders and managers should use a board for standardized work by assigning cards for each job on the production line, each organized by job number in the area, including a map. The cards should have the following yes-no questions:

- Is the standardized work chart accurate in its times?
- Is the takt correct?
- Is the operator following the steps in sequence?
- Is the operator following the steps in timing?
- Are all the key points being followed?

Each day, the group leader should take one card, pull the job breakdown sheet and observe, looking for deviations from standardized work. Any deviations lead to an answer of “No” and should include a written explanation. The managers also should randomly pick a card each day and do the same thing. In the case of any differences, the managers would go through the job with the group leader. This is highly effective. It assumes you are building to takt and following standardized work, at least to a degree, and that everything is kept up to date. It’s unusual for everyone to follow

standard work perfectly, so there should be observed deviations that will lead to problem-solving.

The right way and the wrong way

Real improvement only takes place by focusing on the front line, directly observing the conditions under which work is done. For example, standardized work for a factory floor cannot be created at a desk in the engineering offices; it must be defined and revised at the gemba. And engineering managers know that standardization of work is the foundation for quality and continuous improvement.

Unfortunately, some engineers and consultants try to implement standard operating procedures created in offices or brought from other companies. Such external SOPs must be adapted, modified and improved to match the company’s current situation and process conditions. Besides, pushing SOPs without getting the front-line people involved in sharing ideas for improvement will end with a process failure. Workers must contribute to creating those SOPs. They should believe that the standardization of work is not an order to follow but something to facilitate their work, making it easier and safer.

Another improvement tool is value stream mapping, which is used to get one-piece flow of product, increase delivery rates to meet customer demands, improve value-added work, remove wastes, improve quality, shorten lead-times and reduce work-in-process inventory. Improving the value stream of the process and creating value stream maps requires some basics:

- Recognize customer needs, what adds value and what does not.
- Measurable objectives, such as reducing lead-times, reduce costs and improve quality.
- Draw the current state map, present the process steps and process flow, point out the value-added and the non-value-added work on the chart.

- Draw the future state map, showing the eliminated non-value-added work.
- Implement the plan: Define the requirements, the training, the timeframe and the working team.
- Do the plan.
- Evaluate the results, set metrics, and keep tracking the progress visually.

Drawing the current state map requires deep observation of the situation and some on-site measurements. The working team physically walks through the process, discusses the process with the employees to obtain insight and bring issues to the surface, and collects ideas for improvement.

When drawing the future state map, it is best to draw all ideas for improvement from the working team, allowing the people who manage the work and have intensive experience with the process to share their ideas. Front-line employees who do the work every day often have intimate knowledge about what hampers their productivity, so let them share their ideas on ways to improve.

Lean leaders, executives and managers must do their part by avoiding common inappropriate actions during the value stream mapping process:

Standardized work for a factory floor cannot be created at a desk in the engineering offices.

- Don’t treat the VSM as a tool for process improvement. Remember, it’s a method to ensure that process improvement efforts do three things: Fit together from process to process so that a flowing value stream is developed; match up with the organization’s targets; and serve the requirements of the external customers.
- Don’t focus on maximizing the efficiency of an individual process without understanding the real situation. For example, maximizing the material flow through production processes using small batches will put more effort and load on the transportation department, and the crew will have to make more batches.

- Don't jump to the do phase without spending enough time gathering facts, collecting people's ideas and training everyone. Processes tend to slip back if people have not been trained on the culture of continuous improvement. People who do the work each day must be allowed to express their ideas for improving the process to produce the future state map. They should believe the changes will facilitate their work, making it easier and safer.
- Senior managers should not use metrics to evaluate results and control employee performance without understanding the obstacles that need to be removed to get stable results. Managers should act as facilitators for the improvement process. Metrics should be used by the employees themselves to measure their progress and define the requirements of the next step.

Gemba develops future leaders

Toyota believes that employees can learn more by doing, by understanding the situation through grasping the reality of the gemba. Ideally, this means teaching on the shop floor, in the office or at the shipping dock rather than at a formal training meeting. At Toyota, the process of fixing problems is used to teach a new way of thinking.

At Toyota, every leader takes the responsibility of developing another leader. Leaders who know how the process works coach their mentees on problem-solving and process improvement methods. The rule is that leaders cannot teach what they cannot do. In Japan, they don't teach management in classrooms, as most learning happens at the gemba. As presented by Jeffrey K. Liker in his book *The Toyota Way to Lean Leadership*, the learning process at Toyota is called shu ha ri, three terms that refer to three stages of learning.

Shu means to protect. In this phase, students are coached on the fundamentals under the watchful eye of the master. Ha means to break away. In this

phase, the student has more freedom to practice unsupervised. The master may check on her; the student can apply the rules creatively but will follow the standard rigidly.

Ri means freedom, and in this phase, rules and behaviors have become so ingrained that the student no longer thinks about them consciously. These students are now in the position to develop their own understanding.

Think about the work standard. A worker first must learn how to assemble parts on-site by following the standard work procedures. He will learn by doing. In the shu stage, he will see how the work is done and try to follow the teacher. The worker will practice the job continuously until he reaches the second step, ha. The teacher will keep monitoring him until he reaches the final stage, ri. At this stage, the worker can observe the overall working procedures and take the responsibility to improve them.

By coaching and mentoring people on processes at the gemba and using real problems to improve leadership skills, Toyota's employees and managers become more professional at solving issues in the future while developing other leaders. Mike Rother presents a great example in his *Toyota Kata* book. In chapter eight, the mentor used a real quality problem in the assembly line to improve the skills of the mentee. Although the mentor figured out the solution quickly, he never told the mentee. Instead, the mentor allowed the mentee a degree of freedom to think and develop his own ideas about solving the problem. This shows how to transfer the mentee from the ha phase to the ri phase.

Gemba aligns plans and goals

Nowadays, companies hire senior managers who have the capability and experience to improve the process and achieve financial targets. Those managers will set targets that cascade down to the operational level. But what happens when those managers are far from the actual situation at the gemba?

Even managers with experience in industrial manufacturing probably don't know about the current situation or how to sustain improvement based on their new company's current state. Conditions differ from one company to another. So targets that come down from above become magical targets, impossible to achieve because of the current situation, the culture, the process conditions or some other obstacles that need to be resolved first. Discovering those obstacles requires frequent gemba visits.

Many still think of lean as a toolkit, copying and pasting techniques based on how they work in Toyota and other successful organizations. A few have realized that lean is not about tools or approaches. True lean requires changing culture, developing leaders and properly understanding human behavior.

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Managers who have spent enough time at the gemba should help set targets using an open-mind process called hoshin kanri. Toyota ensures that all leaders involved in the process of setting targets have spent enough time at the gemba to understand the real situation.

Take the situation where senior management set a target of increasing the value-added percentage in a specific work process by 20 percent via a one-week kaizen effort. The senior manager told operational leaders: "Here is what we need and how your performance will be judged. Go do your jobs and bring back the results, whatever it takes."

The manager of the operations department knew how to remove wastes on the shop floor and achieve the demanded improvement. However, the front-line workers lacked knowledge of lean theory and other improvement methodologies. They were not capable of managing their work under the new situation. All efforts spent on improvement were lost after a short while, and the new process wasn't sustained. One week was not enough to plan the achievement, share the ideas with others, train the workers, and

implement the best solution. The new senior manager did not know the real situation, which prevented him from preparing a good plan.

Usually, such managers don't pay attention to the plans or how the work will be done as long as they get results. This leads to the current state in many enterprises, where companies suffer through short-lived improvements and limited sustainability with lean methodologies.

Unfortunately, many business schools still teach the approach of management by results, also called management by objectives. The bad habits of modern management make the lean journey harder.

The process of setting targets and pursuing the achievement cannot be separated. If a manager sets targets, she must understand the real means (the plan) to get there. This understanding comes only from daily experience at the gemba.

Gemba benefits workers and customers

In the traditional working environment, there often is a lack of trust between the laborers at the operational level and the top managers. Managers treat laborers like machines and overburden them to achieve corporate goals. The rule is, "Extract the maximum for lowest fees." And laborers try to preserve their jobs with tricks that keep them working with their preferred method, constraining any improvement.

Gemba walks help to maintain good relations and a foundation of trust between top management and front-line workers. During these walks, leaders should watch the working environment to see if something is wrong that could affect employee safety, make sure operators are not performing risky acts, and monitor the working environment for problems that prevent laborers from doing their jobs smoothly (such as a lack of available tools, no spare parts, delays in transporting needed material and unsafe equipment in the working area).

Leaders also should give high priority and commitment to workplace cleaning and organization (like doing a 5S organization). A clean, safe and comfortable environment lets laborers know that everyone in the company is committed to employee safety and satisfaction.

These good attitudes permeate throughout the organization. Instead of just things to accomplish, targets become ways to drive improvements and make processes safer and easier, increasing employee productivity.

All this increases employee morale. A clean, orderly place will make employees proud to come to work. It also will give a good impression to customers who are visiting the company.

The theory of go and see also applies to designing products for your customers. Take another book by Liker, his best-selling *The Toyota Way*. Liker describes how Toyota used the genchi genbustu process to design what was suitable for drivers in the United States.

When Japan was preparing to revamp its Sienna minivan, Yuji Yokoya was the chief engineer responsible for the redesign. Yokoya and his assistant Andy Lund drove 53,000 miles throughout the U.S., Canada and Mexico to figure out what design changes would benefit customers, changes that wouldn't occur to a Japanese engineer living in Japan.

Yokoya noted that places in the U.S. are farther away than cities and attractions in Japan, so he learned the value of cup holders. If someone buys a can of juice in Japan, it is more common to drink the beverage outside of the car, whereas Americans making long trips usually consume their drinks in the vehicle. So Yokoya designed two cup holders per person. And after Yokoya drove the narrow streets of Santa Fe, N.M., he found it hard to turn corners. So the engineering team tightened the turning radius.

Leader considerations

A few considerations mentioned first by Rother in *Toyota Kata* can help leaders get full value out of their gemba walks:

- Bring your tools: A stopwatch, graph paper, pencil, eraser and calculator.
- Approach the process via the team leader and the supervisor.
- Introduce yourself, explain what you are doing, and don't interrupt operators while they are working.
- Explain that you are watching the work, not the operator.
- Show any notes you have taken.
- Say "thank you" before you leave.
- Keep hands out of pockets on the shop floor. People are working hard, and jamming your hands in your pockets sends a too casual message. A better message is, "We are all working hard for the customer."

Because no improvement is carried out at offices, all improvement phases should be designed, planned and implemented where the work is done. Lean principles cannot succeed without real problem-solving and continuous improvement at the place where the work is done.

It can be a great shock for people working in the system to make problems visible. People tend to hide their problems from bosses. Avoiding this situation requires changing the culture, making sure that management isn't based on blaming others. Developing a no-blame culture that brings problems into the light of day requires an atmosphere where employees do not fear retribution or embarrassment.

But a no-blame culture does not accept and repeat problems without investigation. Going to the gemba solves current problems and develops future leaders who can make sure a culture of continuous improvement is nurtured and grows. ❖

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